

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
Getting Started with Deep Learning - Slides	Slides (PDF)	Slides presented during the webinar	Included in this Zenodo record
Getting started with deep learning	Recording (YouTube video)	Recording of the live webinar presentation	Available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel https://youtu.be/l1TmPnZUuiQ